

APPLICATIONS OF SOFT SET THEORY TO THE SUBALGEBRAS OF *CI*-ALGEBRAS

OHOU D. ALSHAHRANI, AMANI D. ALJOHANI, GHULAM MUHIUDDIN*, MARAM A. ALBALAWI
AND SALIH AH L. ALSHARARI

ABSTRACT. In this paper, the applicability of soft set theory to subalgebras of *CI*-algebras is investigated. *CI*-algebras are utilized in algebraic logic and computer science. Soft set theory is a framework for dealing with ambiguous or imprecise information. We employ soft sets to investigate the intersection and union of subalgebras, among other properties of subalgebras of *CI*-algebras. We demonstrate that soft set theory is a valuable tool for analyzing subalgebras of *CI*-algebras and developing new results in this domain. This paper contributes to the comprehension of soft set theory and its applications in *CI*-algebras with the findings presented herein.

1. INTRODUCTION

Soft set theory, introduced by Molodtsov in 1999 [17], is a mathematical framework that provides a flexible and intuitive way to handle uncertain or imprecise information. It has gained significant attention in various fields, including decision-making, data mining, pattern recognition, and artificial intelligence. Soft set theory allows for the representation and analysis of vague or incomplete information through the concept of a soft set, which is a generalization of classical set theory.

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in combining different mathematical theories to gain new insights and solve complex problems. The combination of soft set theory and BCI-algebras has the potential to provide a deeper understanding of the properties and behaviour of BCI-algebras in the presence of uncertain information.

Kim and Kim introduced the concept of a *BE*-algebra to generalize a BCK-algebra and studied its numerous properties [12]. In an attempt to further develop the concept of *BE*-algebras, Meng introduced *CI*-algebras as a generalization [16]. Subsequently, Kim examined the ideal theory and attributes of *CI*-algebras [11].

This research builds upon previous work in the fields of soft sets and BCI-algebras. Aktas and Cagman [1] introduced the concept of soft sets and their applications in various

2010 *Mathematics Subject Classification.* 03G25, 06F35, 06D72.

Key words and phrases. Soft set; *CI*-algebra; soft *CI*-algebra.

Received: March 15, 2023. Accepted: April 25, 2023. Published: June 30, 2023.

*Corresponding author.

mathematical structures. Huang [5] provided a comprehensive study of BCI-algebras and their properties. Jun [6] extended the concept of soft sets to BCK/BCI-algebras. Jun and Park [9] explored the applications of soft sets in the ideal theory of BCK/BCI-algebras.

Fuzzy soft sets were introduced by Maji et al. [14, 15], who also explored their application in decision-making problems. Since then, research on the theory of soft sets has progressed rapidly. For instance, Jun et al. [7] studied intersection-soft filters in R_0 -algebras, while Roh and Jun [26] investigated positive implicative ideals in BCK -algebras using intersectional soft sets. Also, Akram [2] introduced the notion of fuzzy soft Lie algebras. Similarly, Roy et al. [27] applied fuzzy soft sets to decision-making problems, and Aygünoğlu et al. [4] proposed and studied the concept of a fuzzy soft group. Moreover, Jun et al. [8] introduced the notion of fuzzy soft BCK/BCI -algebras (also known as FSB-algebras) by applying the theory of fuzzy soft sets to BCK/BCI -algebras. Additionally, numerous studies have been conducted by Muhiuddin et al. that explore the application of soft set theory to various algebraic structures [3, 10, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25].

In this paper, we build upon the existing literature by focusing specifically on the relationship between soft sets and subalgebra in CI -algebras. We aim to provide a comprehensive analysis of this relationship and establish important results that contribute to the understanding of soft set theory in the context of CI -algebras. The applicability of soft set theory to CI -algebraic subalgebras is examined in this study. Specifically, by utilising the idea of soft sets, we investigate several subalgebraic qualities like their intersection and union. Additionally, we define a soft ideal as a soft set of a CI -algebra. It is our intention to demonstrate how soft set theory can be a useful tool for studying and comprehending subalgebras of CI -algebras.

Following is how the current paper is structured: The terms and characteristics relevant to soft sets and CI -algebras are covered in Section 2 in detail. Soft set operations are used in Section 3 to examine the intersection, union and other results based on soft CI -algebras. Our conclusions and possible future study directions are summarised in Section 4 for the conclusion.

2. PRELIMINARIES

A type $(2, \theta)$ algebra $(L_0; *, 1)$ is referred to as a *wwwCI*-algebra (briefly, *CI-A*) if it fulfills the following criteria:

- (CI1) $m_1 * m_1 = 1$,
- (CI2) $1 * m_1 = m_1$,
- (CI3) $m_1 * (m_2 * m_3) = m_2 * (m_1 * m_3)$,

for all $m_1, m_2, m_3 \in L_0$. A *CI-A* $(L_0; *, 1)$ is said to be *transitive* if it satisfies:

$$(\forall m_1, m_2, m_3 \in L_0) ((m_2 * m_3) * ((m_1 * m_2) * (m_1 * m_3)) = 1). \quad (2.1)$$

A *CI-A* $(L_0; *, 1)$ is said to be *self-distributive* if it satisfies:

$$(\forall m_1, m_2, m_3 \in L_0) (m_1 * (m_2 * m_3) = (m_1 * m_2) * (m_1 * m_3)). \quad (2.2)$$

Note that every self-distributive *CI-A* is a transitive *CI-A* (see [11]).

A non-empty subset \hat{I} of a *CI-A* $(L_0; *, 1)$ is called an *ideal* of L_0 (see [11]) if it satisfies:

- (I1) $(\forall m_1, m_2 \in L_0) (m_2 \in \hat{I} \Rightarrow m_1 * m_2 \in \hat{I})$,
- (I2) $(\forall m_1, r_0, s_0 \in L_0) (r_0, s_0 \in \hat{I} \Rightarrow (r_0 * (s_0 * m_1)) * m_1 \in \hat{I})$.

Molodtsov [17] presented the following definition of a soft set. Consider an initial universe set \widehat{U} and a set of parameters E , with $\mathcal{Y}(\widehat{U})$ denoting the power set of \widehat{U} . Let $\widehat{J}_1 \subset E$.

Definition 2.1. A pair $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$ is defined as a *soft set* over \widehat{U} , where $\tilde{\rho}$ is a mapping given by $\tilde{\rho} : \widehat{J}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}(\widehat{U})$.

Consider two soft sets over a common universe \widehat{U} , namely $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$ and $(\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_2)$. The intersection of these two soft sets is defined as the soft set (\tilde{h}, \widehat{W}) , which satisfies the following conditions:

Definition 2.2. [13] The *intersection* of $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$ and $(\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_2)$ is given by the soft set (\tilde{h}, \widehat{W}) , where:

- (i) $\widehat{W} = \widehat{J}_1 \cap \widehat{J}_2$, and
- (ii) For every $e \in \widehat{W}$, we have $\tilde{h}(e) = \tilde{\rho}(e)$ or $\tilde{\sigma}(e)$, since both are the same set.

This intersection is denoted as $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1) \tilde{\cap} (\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_2) = (\tilde{h}, \widehat{W})$.

Definition 2.3. [13] The *union* of $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$ and $(\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_2)$ is given by the soft set (\tilde{h}, \widehat{W}) , where:

- (i) $\widehat{W} = \widehat{J}_1 \cup \widehat{J}_2$,
- (ii) For all $e \in \widehat{W}$,

$$\tilde{h}(e) = \begin{cases} \tilde{\rho}(e) & \text{if } e \in \widehat{J}_1 \setminus \widehat{J}_2, \\ \tilde{\sigma}(e) & \text{if } e \in \widehat{J}_2 \setminus \widehat{J}_1, \\ \tilde{\rho}(e) \cup \tilde{\sigma}(e) & \text{if } e \in \widehat{J}_1 \cap \widehat{J}_2. \end{cases}$$

This union is denoted as $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1) \tilde{\cup} (\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_2) = (\tilde{h}, \widehat{W})$.

Definition 2.4. If $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$ and $(\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_2)$ are two soft sets over a common universe \widehat{U} , then the operation "AND" between them, denoted by $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1) \tilde{\wedge} (\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_2)$, is defined as $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1) \tilde{\wedge} (\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_2) = (\tilde{h}, \widehat{J}_1 \times \widehat{J}_2)$, where $\tilde{h}(\beta, \beta) = \tilde{\rho}(\beta) \cap \tilde{\sigma}(\beta)$ for all $(\beta, \beta) \in \widehat{J}_1 \times \widehat{J}_2$.

Definition 2.5. [13] If $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$ and $(\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_2)$ are two soft sets over a common universe \widehat{U} , then the operation "OR" between them, denoted as $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1) \tilde{\vee} (\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_2)$, is defined as $(\tilde{h}, \widehat{J}_1 \times \widehat{J}_2)$, where $\tilde{h}(\beta, \beta) = \tilde{\rho}(\beta) \cup \tilde{\sigma}(\beta)$ for all $(\beta, \beta) \in \widehat{J}_1 \times \widehat{J}_2$.

Definition 2.6. [13] Two soft sets $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$ and $(\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_2)$ over a common universe \widehat{U} are said to have a soft subset relationship, denoted by $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1) \tilde{\subset} (\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_2)$, if they satisfy the following conditions:

- (i) $\widehat{J}_1 \subset \widehat{J}_2$,
- (ii) For every $\varepsilon \in \widehat{J}_1$, $\tilde{\rho}(\varepsilon)$ and $\tilde{\sigma}(\varepsilon)$ are identical approximations.

For a soft set $(\tilde{\rho}, L_0)$ over \widehat{U} and a subset γ of \widehat{U} , the γ -*inclusive set* of $(\tilde{\rho}, L_0)$, denoted by $(\tilde{\rho}; \gamma) \supseteq$, is defined to be the set

$$(\tilde{\rho}; \gamma) \supseteq := \{m_1 \in L_0 \mid \gamma \subseteq \tilde{\rho}(m_1)\}.$$

3. SOFT CI-ALGEBRAS

In the subsequent discussion, we consider a CI -A denoted as L_0 and a nonempty set denoted as \widehat{J}_1 . We use the symbol R to represent an arbitrary binary relation between an element of \widehat{J}_1 and an element of L_0 . Specifically, R is a subset of the Cartesian product

$\widehat{J}_1 \times L_0$, unless stated otherwise. A set-valued function $\tilde{\rho} : \widehat{J}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(L_0)$ can be formally defined as $\tilde{\rho}(m_1) = \{m_2 \in L_0 \mid m_1 R m_2\}$ for all $m_1 \in \widehat{J}_1$. The pair $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$ can be considered as a soft set over L_0 . The order of an element m_1 in a CI-A L_0 is defined as $o(m_1)$ and is given by $o(m_1) = \min\{n \in \mathbb{N} \mid 0 * m_1^n = 0\}$.

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Definition 3.1. $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$ is an soft CI-A over L_0 if $\tilde{\rho}(m_1)$ is a subalgebra of L_0 for every $m_1 \in \widehat{J}_1$.

Let's illustrate this definition with the examples below.

Example 3.2. Let $X = \{\theta, r_0, s_0, t_0, p_0\}$ be a BCK-algebra with the following Cayley table:

*	θ	r_0	s_0	t_0	p_0
θ	θ	θ	θ	θ	θ
r_0	r_0	θ	r_0	r_0	r_0
s_0	s_0	s_0	θ	s_0	s_0
t_0	t_0	t_0	t_0	θ	t_0
p_0	p_0	p_0	p_0	p_0	θ

Let $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$ be a soft set over L_0 , where $\widehat{J}_1 = L_0$ and $\tilde{\rho} : \widehat{J}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(L_0)$ is a set-valued function defined by

$$\tilde{\rho}(m_1) = \{m_2 \in L_0 \mid m_1 R m_2 \Leftrightarrow m_2 \in m_1^{-1} I\}$$

for all $m_1 \in \widehat{J}_1$ where $\hat{I} = \{\theta, r_0\}$ and $m_1^{-1} \hat{I} = \{m_2 \in L_0 \mid m_1 \wedge m_2 \in \hat{I}\}$. Then $\tilde{\rho}(\theta) = \tilde{\rho}(r_0) = L_0$, $\tilde{\rho}(s_0) = \{\theta, r_0, t_0, p_0\}$, $\tilde{\rho}(t_0) = \{\theta, r_0, s_0, p_0\}$, and $\tilde{\rho}(p_0) = \{\theta, r_0, s_0, t_0\}$ are subalgebras of L_0 . Therefore $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$ is a soft CI-A over L_0 .

Let \widehat{J}_1 be a fuzzy CI-SubA of L_0 with membership function $\mu_{\widehat{J}_1}$. Let us consider the family of β -level sets for the function $\mu_{\widehat{J}_1}$ given by

$$\tilde{\rho}(\beta) = \{m_1 \in L_0 \mid \mu_{\widehat{J}_1}(x) \geq \beta\}, \beta \in [0, 1].$$

Then $\tilde{\rho}(\beta)$ is a CI-SubA of L_0 . If we know the family $\tilde{\rho}$, we can find the functions $\mu_{\widehat{J}_1}(x)$ by means of the following formula:

$$\mu_{\widehat{J}_1}(m_1) = \sup\{\beta \in [0, 1] \mid m_1 \in \tilde{\rho}(\beta)\}.$$

Thus, every fuzzy CI-SubA \widehat{J}_1 may be considered as the soft CI-A $(\tilde{\rho}, [0, 1])$.

Theorem 3.1. Let $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$ be a soft CI-A over L_0 . If \widehat{J}_2 is a subset of \widehat{J}_1 , then $(\tilde{\rho}|_{\widehat{J}_2}, \widehat{J}_2)$ is a soft CI-A over L_0 .

Proof. Straightforward. □

The following example shows that there exists a soft set $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$ over L_0 such that

- (i) $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$ is not a soft CI-A over L_0 .
- (ii) there exists a subset \widehat{J}_2 of \widehat{J}_1 such that $(\tilde{\rho}|_{\widehat{J}_2}, \widehat{J}_2)$ is a soft CI-A over L_0 .

Theorem 3.2. If $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$ and $(\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_2)$ are two soft CI-As over L_0 with a non-empty intersection $\widehat{J}_1 \cap \widehat{J}_2$, then their intersection $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1) \cap (\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_2)$ is also a soft CI-A over L_0 .

Proof. Let (\tilde{h}, \widehat{W}) be the intersection of $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$ and $(\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_2)$, where $\widehat{W} = \widehat{J}_1 \cap \widehat{J}_2$ and $\tilde{h}(m_1) = \tilde{\rho}(m_1)$ or $\tilde{\sigma}(m_1)$ for all $m_1 \in \widehat{W}$. Since $\tilde{h} : \widehat{W} \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(L_0)$ is a mapping,

(\tilde{h}, \widehat{W}) is a soft set over L_0 . As $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$ and $(\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_2)$ are soft CI -As over L_0 , we have $\tilde{h}(m_1) = \tilde{\rho}(m_1)$ or $\tilde{h}(m_1) = \tilde{\sigma}(m_1)$ is a CI -SubA of L_0 for all $m_1 \in \widehat{W}$. Therefore, $(\tilde{h}, \widehat{W}) = (\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1) \tilde{\cap} (\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_2)$ is a soft CI -A over L_0 . \square

Corollary 3.3. *Let $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$ and $(\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_1)$ be two soft CI -As over L_0 . Then their intersection $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1) \tilde{\cap} (\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_1)$ is a soft CI -A over L_0 .*

Proof. Straightforward. \square

Theorem 3.4. *If $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$ and $(\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_1)$ are two soft CI -As over L_0 with disjoint sets \widehat{J}_1 and \widehat{J}_2 , then their union $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1) \tilde{\cup} (\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_1)$ is a soft CI -A over L_0 .*

Proof. Let (\tilde{h}, \widehat{W}) be the union of $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$ and $(\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_2)$, where $\widehat{W} = \widehat{J}_1 \cup \widehat{J}_2$ and for every $e \in \widehat{W}$,

$$\tilde{h}(e) = \begin{cases} \tilde{\rho}(e) & \text{if } e \in \widehat{J}_1 \setminus \widehat{J}_2, \\ \tilde{\sigma}(e) & \text{if } e \in \widehat{J}_2 \setminus \widehat{J}_1, \\ \tilde{\rho}(e) \cup \tilde{\sigma}(e) & \text{if } e \in \widehat{J}_1 \cap \widehat{J}_2. \end{cases}$$

Since \widehat{J}_1 and \widehat{J}_2 are disjoint sets, for every $x \in \widehat{W}$ we have that either $m_1 \in \widehat{J}_1 \setminus \widehat{J}_2$ or $m_1 \in \widehat{J}_2 \setminus \widehat{J}_1$. If $m_1 \in \widehat{J}_1 \setminus \widehat{J}_2$, then $\tilde{h}(m_1) = \tilde{\rho}(m_1)$ is a CI -SubA of L_0 since $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$ is a soft CI -A over L_0 . Similarly, if $m_1 \in \widehat{J}_2 \setminus \widehat{J}_1$, then $\tilde{h}(m_1) = \tilde{\sigma}(m_1)$ is a CI -SubA of L_0 since $(\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_2)$ is a soft CI -A over L_0 . Hence, $(\tilde{h}, \widehat{W}) = (\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1) \tilde{\cup} (\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_1)$ is a soft CI -A over L_0 . \square

Theorem 3.5. *If $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$ and $(\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_2)$ are both soft CI -As over L_0 , then $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1) \tilde{\wedge} (\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_2)$ is also soft.*

Proof. By means of Definition 2.4, we know that

$$(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1) \tilde{\wedge} (\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_2) = (\tilde{h}, \widehat{J}_1 \times \widehat{J}_2),$$

where $\tilde{h}(m_1, m_2) = \tilde{\rho}(m_1) \cap \tilde{\sigma}(m_2)$ for all $(m_1, m_2) \in \widehat{J}_1 \times \widehat{J}_2$. Since $\tilde{\rho}(m_1)$ and $\tilde{\sigma}(m_2)$ are CI -SubAs of L_0 , the intersection $\tilde{\rho}(m_1) \cap \tilde{\sigma}(m_2)$ is also a CI -SubA of L_0 . Hence $\tilde{h}(m_1, m_2)$ is a CI -SubA of L_0 for all $(m_1, m_2) \in \widehat{J}_1 \times \widehat{J}_2$, and therefore $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1) \tilde{\wedge} (\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_2) = (\tilde{h}, \widehat{J}_1 \times \widehat{J}_2)$ is a soft CI -A over L_0 . \square

Definition 3.3. In the context of soft CI -As over L_0 , a soft CI -A $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$ is considered *trivial* if $\tilde{\rho}(m_1) = 0$ for all $m_1 \in \widehat{J}_1$, and it is considered *whole* if $\tilde{\rho}(m_1) = L_0$ for all $m_1 \in \widehat{J}_1$.

Example 3.4. Consider the BCI-algebra $L_0 = \{\theta, r_0, s_0, t_0\}$ introduced in Example 3.2. For $\widehat{J}_1 = L_0$, we define $\tilde{\rho} : \widehat{J}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(L_0)$ as follows:

$$\tilde{\rho}(m_1) = \{\theta\} \cup \{m_2 \in L_0 \mid m_1 R m_2, \Leftrightarrow, o(m_1) = o(m_2)\}$$

for every $m_1 \in \widehat{J}_1$. It can be observed that $\tilde{\rho}(x) = L_0$ for all $m_1 \in \widehat{J}_1$, indicating that $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$ forms a whole soft BCI-algebra over L_0 .

Consider a mapping, denoted as $\bar{\eta} : L_0 \rightarrow Q_0$, which maps CI -As. Now, suppose we have a soft set $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$ over L_0 . In this case, $(\bar{\eta}(\tilde{\rho}), \widehat{J}_1)$ represents a soft set over Q_0 , where $\bar{\eta}(\tilde{\rho}) : \widehat{J}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(Q_0)$ is defined as $\bar{\eta}(\tilde{\rho})(m_1) = \bar{\eta}(\tilde{\rho}(m_1))$ for any m_1 belonging to \widehat{J}_1 .

Lemma 3.6. *Let $\bar{\eta} : L_0 \rightarrow Q_0$ be a homomorphism of CI -As. If $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$ is a soft CI -A over L_0 , then $(\bar{\eta}(\tilde{\rho}), \widehat{J}_1)$ is a soft CI -A over Q_0 .*

Proof. For every $m_1 \in \widehat{J}_1$, we have $\bar{\eta}(\tilde{\rho})(m_1) = \bar{\eta}(\tilde{\rho}(m_1))$ is a *CI-SubA* of Q_0 since $\tilde{\rho}(m_1)$ is a *CI-SubA* of L_0 and its homomorphic image is also a *CI-SubA* of Q_0 . Hence $(\bar{\eta}(\tilde{\rho}), \widehat{J}_1)$ is a soft *CI-A* over Q_0 . \square

Theorem 3.7. Let $\bar{\eta} : L_0 \rightarrow Q_0$ be a homomorphism of *CI-As* and let $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$ be a soft *CI-A* over L_0 .

- (i) If $\tilde{\rho}(m_1) = \ker(\bar{\eta})$ for all $m_1 \in \widehat{J}_1$, then $(\bar{\eta}(\tilde{\rho}), \widehat{J}_1)$ is the trivial soft *CI-A* over Q_0 .
- (ii) If $\bar{\eta}$ is onto and $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$ is whole, then $(\bar{\eta}(\tilde{\rho}), \widehat{J}_1)$ is the whole soft *CI-A* over Q_0 .

Proof. (i) Assume that $\tilde{\rho}(m_1) = \ker(\bar{\eta})$ for all $m_1 \in \widehat{J}_1$. Then $\bar{\eta}(\tilde{\rho})(m_1) = \bar{\eta}(\tilde{\rho}(m_1)) = \{0_{Q_0}\}$ for all $m_1 \in \widehat{J}_1$. Hence $(\bar{\eta}(\tilde{\rho}), \widehat{J}_1)$ is the trivial soft *CI-A* over Q_0 by Lemma 3.6 and Definition 3.3.

(ii) Suppose that $\bar{\eta}$ is onto and $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$ is whole. Then $\tilde{\rho}(m_1) = L_0$ for all $m_1 \in \widehat{J}_1$, and so $\bar{\eta}(\tilde{\rho})(m_1) = \bar{\eta}(\tilde{\rho}(m_1)) = \bar{\eta}(L_0) = Q_0$ for all $m_1 \in \widehat{J}_1$. It follows from Lemma 3.6 and Definition 3.3 that $(\bar{\eta}(\tilde{\rho}), \widehat{J}_1)$ is the whole soft *CI-A* over Q_0 . \square

Definition 3.5. Let $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$ and $(\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_2)$ be two soft *CI-As* over L_0 . Then $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$ is called a *soft subalgebra* (briefly, *S-SubA*) of $(\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_2)$, denoted by $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1) \prec (\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_2)$, if it satisfies:

- (i) $\widehat{J}_1 \subset \widehat{J}_2$,
- (ii) $\tilde{\rho}(m_1)$ is a *CI-SubA* of $\tilde{\sigma}(m_1)$ for all $m_1 \in \widehat{J}_1$.

Example 3.6. Let $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$ be a soft BCK-algebra over L_0 which is given in Example 3.4. Let $\widehat{J}_2 = \{r_0, t_0, p_0\}$ be a subset of \widehat{J}_1 and let $G : \widehat{J}_2 \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}(L_0)$ be a set-valued function defined by

$$\tilde{\sigma}(m_1) = \{m_2 \in L_0 \mid m_1 R m_2 \Leftrightarrow m_2 \in m_1^{-1} \hat{I}\}$$

for all $m_1 \in \widehat{J}_2$, where $\hat{I} = \{\theta, r_0\}$ and $m_1^{-1} \hat{I} = \{m_2 \in L_0 \mid m_1 \wedge m_2 \in \hat{I}\}$. Then $\tilde{\sigma}(r_0) = L_0$, $\tilde{\sigma}(t_0) = \{\theta, r_0, s_0, p_0\}$ and $\tilde{\sigma}(p_0) = \{\theta, r_0, s_0, t_0\}$ are BCK-subalgebras of $\tilde{\rho}(r_0)$, $\tilde{\rho}(t_0)$ and $\tilde{\rho}(p_0)$, respectively. Hence $(\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_2)$ is a *S-SubA* of $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$.

Theorem 3.8. Let $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$ and $(\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_1)$ be two soft *CI-As* over L_0 .

- (i) If $\tilde{\rho}(m_1) \subset \tilde{\sigma}(m_1)$ for all $m_1 \in \widehat{J}_1$, then $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1) \prec (\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_1)$.
- (ii) If $\widehat{J}_2 = \{\theta\}$ and $(\tilde{h}, \widehat{J}_2)$, $(\tilde{\rho}, L_0)$ are soft *CI-As* over L_0 , then $(\tilde{h}, \widehat{J}_2) \prec (\tilde{\rho}, L_0)$.

Proof. Straightforward. \square

Theorem 3.9. Let $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$ be a soft *CI-A* over L_0 and let $(\tilde{\sigma}_1, \widehat{J}_{21})$ and $(\tilde{\sigma}_2, \widehat{J}_{22})$ be *S-SubAs* of $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$. Then

- (i) $(\tilde{\sigma}_1, \widehat{J}_{21}) \tilde{\cap} (\tilde{\sigma}_2, \widehat{J}_{22}) \prec (\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$.
- (ii) $\widehat{J}_{21} \cap \widehat{J}_{22} = \emptyset \Rightarrow (\tilde{\sigma}_1, \widehat{J}_{21}) \tilde{\cup} (\tilde{\sigma}_2, \widehat{J}_{22}) \prec (\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$.

Proof. (i) Using Definition 2.2, we can write

$$(\tilde{\sigma}_1, \widehat{J}_{21}) \tilde{\cap} (\tilde{\sigma}_2, \widehat{J}_{22}) = (\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_2),$$

where $\widehat{J}_2 = \widehat{J}_{21} \cap \widehat{J}_{22}$ and $\tilde{\sigma}(m_1) = \tilde{\sigma}_1(m_1)$ or $\tilde{\sigma}_2(m_1)$ for all $m_1 \in \widehat{J}_2$. Obviously, $\widehat{J}_2 \subset \widehat{J}_1$. Let $m_1 \in \widehat{J}_2$. Then $m_1 \in \widehat{J}_{21}$ and $m_1 \in \widehat{J}_{22}$. If $x \in \widehat{J}_{21}$, then $\tilde{\sigma}(m_1) = \tilde{\sigma}_1(m_1)$ is a *CI-SubA* of $\tilde{\rho}(x)$ since $(\tilde{\sigma}_1, \widehat{J}_{21}) \prec (\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$. If $m_1 \in \widehat{J}_{22}$, then $\tilde{\sigma}(m_1) = \tilde{\sigma}_2(m_1)$ is a *CI-SubA* of $\tilde{\rho}(m_1)$ since $(\tilde{\sigma}_2, \widehat{J}_{22}) \prec (\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$. Hence $(\tilde{\sigma}_1, \widehat{J}_{21}) \tilde{\cap} (\tilde{\sigma}_2, \widehat{J}_{22}) = (\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_2) \prec (\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$.

(ii) Assume that $\widehat{J}_{21} \cap \widehat{J}_{22} = \emptyset$. We can write $(\tilde{\sigma}_1, B_1) \dot{\cup} (\tilde{\sigma}_2, B_2) = (\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_2)$ where $\widehat{J}_2 = B_1 \cup \widehat{J}_{22}$ and

$$\tilde{\sigma}(m_1) = \begin{cases} \tilde{\sigma}_1(m_1) & \text{if } m_1 \in \widehat{J}_{21} \setminus \widehat{J}_{22}, \\ \tilde{\sigma}_2(m_1) & \text{if } m_1 \in \widehat{J}_{22} \setminus \widehat{J}_{21}, \\ \tilde{\sigma}_1(m_1) \cup \tilde{\sigma}_2(m_1) & \text{if } m_1 \in \widehat{J}_{21} \cap \widehat{J}_{22} \end{cases}$$

for all $m_1 \in \widehat{J}_2$. Since $(\tilde{\sigma}_i, \widehat{J}_{2i}) \prec (\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$ for $i = 1, 2$, $\widehat{J}_2 = \widehat{J}_{21} \cup \widehat{J}_{22} \subset \widehat{J}_1$ and $\tilde{\sigma}_i(m_1)$ is a CI -SubA of $\tilde{\rho}(m_1)$ for all $m_1 \in \widehat{J}_{2i}$, $i = 1, 2$. Since $\widehat{J}_{21} \cap \widehat{J}_{22} = \emptyset$, $\tilde{\sigma}(m_1)$ is a CI -SubA of $\tilde{\rho}(m_1)$ for all $m_1 \in B$. Therefore $(\tilde{\sigma}_1, \widehat{J}_{21}) \dot{\cup} (\tilde{\sigma}_2, \widehat{J}_{22}) = (\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_2) \prec (\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$. \square

Theorem 3.10. Let $\bar{\eta} : L_0 \rightarrow Q_0$ be a homomorphism of CI -As and let $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1)$ and $(\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_2)$ be soft CI -As over L_0 . Then

$$(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1) \prec (\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_2) \Rightarrow (\bar{\eta}(\tilde{\rho}), \widehat{J}_1) \prec (\bar{\eta}(\tilde{\sigma}), \widehat{J}_2).$$

Proof. Assume that $(\tilde{\rho}, \widehat{J}_1) \prec (\tilde{\sigma}, \widehat{J}_2)$. Let $m_1 \in \widehat{J}_1$. Then $\widehat{J}_1 \subset \widehat{J}_2$ and $\tilde{\rho}(m_1)$ is a CI -SubA of $\tilde{\sigma}(m_1)$. Since $\bar{\eta}$ is a homomorphism, $\bar{\eta}(\tilde{\rho})(m_1) = \bar{\eta}(\tilde{\rho}(m_1))$ is a CI -SubA of $\bar{\eta}(\tilde{\sigma}(m_1)) = \bar{\eta}(\tilde{\sigma})(m_1)$, and therefore $(\bar{\eta}(\tilde{\rho}), \widehat{J}_1) \prec (\bar{\eta}(\tilde{\sigma}), \widehat{J}_2)$. \square

4. CONCLUSION

This investigation successfully applies soft set theory to CI -algebraic subalgebras and offers new insights into their properties. We can investigate the intersection and union of subalgebras and the notion of a soft ideal formed by a soft set of a CI -algebra, with the help of soft set operations. Our findings create the framework for further research in this area and demonstrate the value of using soft set theory to analyse CI -algebraic subalgebras. The results of this work may have an impact on the development of new algorithms and techniques for handling ambiguous data in CI -algebras. Overall, this work extends our knowledge of soft set theory and its applications in CI -algebras and paves the way for future research in the field.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to express their sincere thanks to the anonymous reviewers for their valuable comments and helpful suggestions, which greatly improved the quality of this paper. The authors extend their appreciation to the Deanship of Scientific Research at University of Tabuk for funding this work through Research no. S-0137-1443.

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OHOUD A. ALSHAHRANI, AMANI D. ALJOHANI, GHULAM MUHIUDDIN*, MARAM A. ALBALAWI AND SALIH AH L. ALSHARARI
 DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS, FACULTY OF SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF TABUK, P.O. BOX 741,, TABUK 71491, SAUDI ARABIA

Email address: 411008512@stu.ut.edu.sa (Ohoud Alshahrani), 411008506@stu.ut.edu.sa (Amani Aljohani), gmuhiuddin@ut.edu.sa (G. Muhiuddin), 411008511@stu.ut.edu.sa (Maram Albalawi), 391000102@stu.ut.edu.sa (Salihah Alsharari)